

**ADDRESSING THE CHALLENGES OF PRACTICAL APPLICATION IN
UNDERGRADUATE EDUCATION PROGRAMS****Abubakar, Fatima Rukayat Musa**School of Early Childhood Care and Primary Education, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi
State, Nigeria.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19595708

Abstract

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19), caused by the novel SARS-CoV-2 virus, emerged in Wuhan, China, in December 2019 and was declared a global pandemic by the World Health Organization in March 2020. The virus primarily spreads through close contact via respiratory droplets, posing significant health risks worldwide. Beyond its public health implications, COVID-19 has profoundly impacted social, economic, and educational systems, disrupting normal operations and learning processes. In Nigeria, where the first case was reported in February 2020, the pandemic led to widespread school closures, a shift to remote learning, and challenges in maintaining educational continuity. This study examines the effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on the education sector, highlighting the disruption of teaching and learning, adaptation strategies, and the broader implications for educational planning and policy.

Keywords: COVID-19, SARS-CoV-2, Education, Pandemic, Nigeria

Introduction

Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is an infectious respiratory disease caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus (WHO, 2020). The Chinese Public Health Authorities first reported cases of respiratory syndrome in Wuhan City, Hube province, China at the end of December, 2019 (Covid-19) and the causative agent is new strain corona virus called the Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome Coronavirus 2 (SARS-2) which has not been previously recognized in Human (Gao & Zhang, 2021). The Covid-19 outbreak was declared a pandemic on 11th March, 2020 World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) declared Covid-19 a pandemic. A pandemic is a diseases that has spread across a large region, for instance, multiple continents or worldwide. The most way that this virus spread is through close contact with already injected person. When already infected person when people with Covid-19 breathe out or cough, the expelled tiny droplets can enter mouth or nose of someone without the virus, causing the spread of injection to occur. The Covid-19 pandemic had negative effect on all aspects of life including the education sector since its outbreak in Wuhan, China in December, 2019 and in Nigeria since 27th of February, 2020. In a process to curtail the spread of the deadly virus, lockdown of public places including tertiary institutions, among others measures were put in place by Nigeria government. During the lockdown, Nigerian students were at disadvantage because most educational institutions in Nigeria still follow the traditional set-up of face-to-face lectures in the normal classroom settings failed, teaching and learning among students suffered a severe setback (Zhang & Gao, 2021). The lockdown caused by Covid-19 pandemic have affected student's morale toward engaging in academic

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related activities such as emotional anxiety, numbing and depression in mind and especially among students who always interacts with each other in class setting (Sekina, 2020). Distancing and that affect the ability of teacher to perform effectively (Obiaka & Adeniran, 2020). American Psychological Association (2021) explained trauma as an emotional response to a terrible event like an accident, rape or natural disaster. Immediately after the event, shock and denial are typical. Longer term reactions include unpredictable emotions, flashbacks, strained relationships and even physical symptoms like headaches or nausea. While these feelings are normal, some people have difficulty moving on with their lives. Psychologists can help these individuals find constructive ways of managing their emotions. A traumatized person can feel a range of emotions both immediately after the event and in the long term. They may feel overwhelmed, helpless, shocked, or have difficulty processing their experiences. Trauma can also cause physical symptoms. Trauma can have long-term effects on the person's well-being. If symptoms persist and do not decrease in severity, it can indicate that the trauma has developed into a mental health disorder called post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) ((Taiwo & Agunbiade, 2014). Regarding the psychological impact of Covid-19, students suffered anxiety symptoms from moderate to severe which affects their self-efficacy (Adewale, Adeniyi, Oluwadamilola, Ojediran, Aremu, Odeyemi, Akintayo, Oluwadamilare, Offrbuiké & Owwoeye, 2021). Furthermore, anxiety is indirectly related to academic performance and directly related to the perception of academic self-efficacy. Students' self-efficacy, namely teachers' beliefs in their ability to effectively handle the tasks, obligations, and challenges related to their professional activity, plays a key role in influencing important academic outcomes (e.g., students' achievement and motivation) and wellbeing in the working environment (Craig, 2021).

Statement of the Problem

The great changes in students' lives and learning situation around the world caused by Covid-19 have brought to society an opportunity to test its capacity to adapt to sudden psychological traumatic situations in which students have been involved in new personal, educational, social and professional environments and tasks and students in colleges and universities have been deeply impacted (Aperribai, Cortaberria, Aguirre, Verche and Borges, 2020). School closures due to COVID-19 have brought significant disruptions to education across the world and Nigeria particular (Eze, Sefotho, Onyishi & Eseadi, 2021). Emerging evidence from some of the region's highest-income countries indicate that the pandemic is giving rise to teaching and losses and increases in inequality on students' academic achievement. To reduce and reverse the long-term negative effects, Nigeria, which is likely to be even harder hit, need to implement teaching and learning recovery programs, protect educational budgets and outcome, and prepare for future shocks by building back better (Obiaka & Adeniran, 2020). In an increasingly dynamic world and ever-changing educational environment, students have been forced to adopt practices, methods, or processes that they have not experienced before. The unexpected appearance of the coronavirus outbreak, which not only caused a vast number of casualties all around the world, but also challenged the whole world and Nigeria

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in particular regarding working context, teaching and learning in particular. Likewise, the usual or common teaching and learning process was also curly toppled by the covid-19, and it promptly intensified the ongoing trends such as shifting of teaching and to online or virtual settings. But a main dissimilarity is that teaching from home was usually dependent on the teachers and students priorities. With the reopen of schools, measures were put in place to prevent the spread of the pandemic disease, these coping measures lead to psychological disorder among tertiary institution students in the world and particularly in Nigeria. The pandemic led the general population to high incidence of health-related problems especially among students who always interact with their teachers, no longer trust the safety of the environment, this accumulated high level of psychological disorder since the beginning of the pandemic such as negative emotion, cognitive and psychological process that occurs in trying to adjust or deal with the stress due to an excessive workload, lack of clear guideline, insufficient training by their teachers which is a major problem and this is because of the increase problems and difficulties imposed by covid-19. Tertiary institutions students are a special group with active life habits based on relationship and contracts, physical, academic based activities and institution activities, travels and gathering. The Covid-19 pandemic emergency changed their life drastically; Shifting from face-to-face classes to online classes is not an easy step for students, especially those who do not have access to laptops and internet facilities at home or those who take courses that cannot be taught online. In addition, students may be uncertain about assessment procedures for online assignments and projects, and will suffer when they do not have an internet facility to participate in the evaluation processes, and this could adversely affect their grade averages and cause to loss of self-efficacy. Such impacts of covid-19 outbreak on students' education and mental health could also affect tertiary institution students in Bauchi state, especially given many precautionary and preventive measures taken to contain the covid-19 outbreak and prevent infection among students. The situation is further exacerbated by the bombardment of media reports related to the issue of the pandemic. On the basis of this, the researcher intends to conduct this study to find out the impact of covid-19 psychological trauma on self-efficacy among students of School of Undergraduate Studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare.

Methodology

An Ex-Post facto research design of the survey type was adopted in this study. The population of the study comprised of all Undergraduate Students of Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare. The population of students is 2,291 (Students Records Office SUS, ASCOE, Azare, 2022). The sample of the study was drawn from the population of all undergraduate students of Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare. The population of students SUS, ASCOE, Azare is 2,291 (Students Records Office SUS, ASCOE, Azare, 2022). The sample of 322 students of School of Undergraduate Studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare was drawn using multistage sampling technique. The selection is in accordance with Research Advisors (2006) assertion who recommended that for the population of 2,000 – 2,499 a sample size of 322 at 95 percent confidence interval at 0.05 alpha level

is adequate for the study. Multistage sampling technique was adopted in the study. The research used two measuring scale as instrument for data collection in the study; The Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-42) developed by (Lovibond and Lovibond, 1995). DASS-42 contains 42 items to measure in three sub-scales of (1) the Depression sub-scale which measures hopelessness, low self-esteem and low positive affect; (2) the Anxiety scale which assess autonomic arousal, musculo-skeletal symptoms, situational anxiety and subjective experience of anxious arousal; and (3) the Stress scale which assess tension, agitation and negative effect. The second instrument is scale is General Self-Efficacy Scale developed by Schwarzer and Jerusalem (1995). GSE is a 10-items psychometric scale designed to assess optimistic self-beliefs to cope with a variety of difficult demands in life. Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-42) is a 42 item self-report scale designed to measure the negative emotional states of depression, anxiety and stress. It was design in three sub-scales of Depression, Anxiety and Stress and in ordinal form with never (0), sometimes (1), Often (2) and Almost always (3). General Self Efficacy Scale (GSE) is a 10-items psychometric scale designed to assess optimistic self-beliefs to cope with a variety of difficult demands in life. It was also designed in ordinal style with Not at all (1), hardly true (2), moderately true (3) and exactly true (4). The total score is calculated by finding the sum of all items. The total ranges between 10 and 40, with a higher score indicating more self-efficacy. Higher scores indicate higher perceived general self-efficacy, lower scores indicate lower perceived general self-efficacy. The depression, anxiety and stress scale DASS-42 was validated by (Kazeem, Jinadu and Adebayo, 2020) in a cross sectional study using 150 Nigerian Army personnel. The result of the study shows that DASS-42 has a good Cronbach's alpha value of 0.89, 0.91 and 0.90 for depression, anxiety and stress subscales. For construct validity, 40 out of 42 items had a good factor loading (.38 to .86). Thus, DASS-42 shows an excellence psychometric properties and it is suitable be used within population. The General Self-Efficacy Scale is correlated to emotion, optimism, and work satisfaction. Negative coefficients were found for depression, stress, health complaints, burnout, and anxiety. 50 Greek asthma out-patients participated in the study. Self-efficacy was assessed, validated and found reliable by (Nikolovgenis, Skordilis, Evangelodimou, Haniotou, Tsamis & Spinou, 2014). Construct validity was tested through differences between groups and Cross-sectional validity through correlation of the GSE score with pulmonary function (FEV₁), asthma control (ACT), QoL (SF36v2), and Borg scale (Pearson's r correlation coefficient). The GSE items showed high internal consistency (Cronbach alpha = 0.95) and test-retest reliability (IR = 0.96). The GSE was valid and reliable to be adopted in any study. Descriptive statistics of frequency counts and percentage was used to analyze the demographic information of the respondents. Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test hypotheses 1 – 3, while linear regression was used in testing hypothesis 4 using latest version of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Result

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Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between Covid-19 anxiety and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State

Table 1: Analysis of PPMC on the Relationship between Covid-19 Anxiety and Self-Efficacy among Students

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	r-cal	Sig.	Dec.
Anxiety	14.2222	6.23334	324			
				-.026	.646	HO Accepted
Self-Efficacy	25.3796	5.87336	324			

Table 1 revealed the analysis result of PPMC on the relationship between Covid-19 anxiety and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State. The table shows that the mean for anxiety was 14.2222 while the mean for self-efficacy was 25.3796. The table also shows that the calculated r value was -.026 which indicates a non-significant negative relationship; therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between Covid-19 stress and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State

Table 2: Analysis of PPMC on the Relationship between Covid-19 Stress and Self-Efficacy among Students

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	r-cal	Sig.	Dec.
Stress	17.0648	6.19838	324			
				.018	.131*	HO Accepted
Self-Efficacy	25.3796	5.87336	324			

Table 2 revealed the analysis result of PPMC on the relationship between Covid-19 stress and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State. The table shows that the mean for stress was 17.0648 while the mean for self-efficacy was 25.3796. The table also shows that the calculated r value was .018 which indicates a non-significant relationship; therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between Covid-19 depression and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu SALEH College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State

Table 3: Analysis of PPMC on the Relationship between Covid-19 Depression and Self-Efficacy among Students

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N	r-cal	Sig.	Dec.
Depression	16.7068	7.41414	324			
				.046	.413	HO Accepted

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Self-Efficacy 25.3796 5.87336 324

Table 3 revealed the analysis result of PPMC on the relationship between Covid-19 depression and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State. The table shows that the mean for depression was 16.7068 while the mean for self-efficacy was 25.3796. The table also shows that the calculated r value was .046 which indicates a non-significant relationship; therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant relationship between psychological trauma of anxiety, stress and depression with self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare, Bauchi State

Table 4: Analysis of Linear Regression on the Predictive Relationship between Psychological Trauma of Anxiety, Stress and Depression with Self-Efficacy among Students

Table 4: Regression Model Summary
Std. Error of the

Model R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Estimate	
1	.142 ^a	.020	.011	5.84126

Table 4 revealed the regression model summary on the predictive relationship between self-efficacy and psychological trauma of anxiety, stress and depression. The table shows that the calculated R square was .020 which indicates that self-efficacy predicts psychological trauma of anxiety, stress and depression at 0.2%

Table 5: Regression ANOVA table

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	223.819	3	74.606	2.187	.090 ^b
	Residual	10918.486	320	34.120		
	Total	11142.306	323			

Table 5 revealed that the calculated p -value was .090 greater than the alpha value of .05, therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Table 6: Regression Coefficient Table

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	23.347	1.283		18.195	.000
	Stress	.125	.053	.131	2.353	.019
	Anxiety	-.042	.053	-.044	-.786	.432

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19 when compared to moderately or mildly anxious students, [$F(2,1516) = 10.60, p < .001$]. The findings of AL-Shahrani and Abdullah M (2021) in an exploratory study on Students' Anxiety during the COVID-19 Pandemic in Saudi Arabia showed that 46.22% of respondents had minimal anxiety, 26.89% had mild anxiety, 12.60% had moderate anxiety, and 14.29% had severe anxiety. The findings indicate that Saudi University students had minimal anxiety issues concomitant to the pandemic. The results also significantly show that students' anxiety or its absence was a factor of gender and the students' current level of education in the university. The result of the findings on hypothesis two shows a non-significant negative relationship between covid-19 psychological trauma of stress and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare. Contrary to the findings Yusuf, Olufunke and Valentine (2015) in their studies on causes and impact of stress on teachers' productivity as expressed by primary school teachers in Nigeria. The result revealed that majority of primary school teachers were stressed on the job and this had negative impacts on their productivity. The study revealed that lack of job satisfaction, inadequate school facilities, were major causes of stress among primary school teachers. The study also revealed that stress had negative impacts on teachers' productivity. The result of the findings on hypothesis three shows a non-significant negative relationship between covid-19 psychological trauma of depression and self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare. In line with the findings of Di Consiglio, Micaela, Sheila Merola, Tiziana Pascucci, Cristiano Violani, and Alessandro Couyoumdjian (2021) on impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Italian University Students' Mental Health: Changes across the Waves. The results of their findings suggest that students experienced moderate to severe levels of depressive, obsessive-compulsive and anxiety symptomatology. About 14% of the sample met the criteria for at least one mental health disorder, but most were not receiving mental health care. During the lockdown, compared with other phases, female students reported worse symptoms in the obsessive-compulsive, interpersonal sensitivity, depression, paranoid ideation, and psychoticism dimensions. Imran, Masood, Ayub and Gandal (2021) conducted a cross-sectional studies on the psychological impact of covid-19 pandemic among postgraduate trainees in Pakistan by qualifying the symptoms of depression, anxiety and acute stress disorder. The results of their findings shows the prevalence of depressive symptoms, generalised anxiety disorder and acute stress disorder were 26.4%, 22.6% and 4.4%, respectively. Female postgraduate trainees, senior trainees and front-line workers reported experiencing more anxiety, depression and acute stress symptoms ($p \text{ value} < 0.001$). Logistic regression showed that being a front-line and senior staff member and female was associated with higher risk of experiencing symptoms of depression, anxiety and acute stress. The result of the findings on hypothesis four reveals that only psychological trauma due to Covid19 among students was stress. It was found that students are suffering moderate to high level of depression, anxiety and stress which is higher than typical levels in ordinary circumstances. When comparing our results regarding depression, anxiety and stress with results from the general populations from seven middle-income countries (Vietnam, China, Iran,

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Malaysia, Philippines, Pakistan, and Thailand), higher levels were found among Jordanian students except those among Thailand who have higher levels (19.74, 18.66–21.95), for depression, anxiety and stress, respectively (Wang et al., 2021). The figures are warranting vulnerability to psychological disturbances and infer a probability of academic and psychosocial deterioration during the quarantine period at home. One explanation could be due to sudden overwhelming academic online assignments and sessions added to social apprehension of lethally and the outbreak of COVID-19. Another explanation could be related to fears that students bear due to uncertainty of their grades and graduation-related issues as supported by Sahu (2020) who have emphasized the fear issues among college students. Academic work is considered a source of anxiety in a normal situation (Shehadeh, Hamdan-Mansour, Halasa, Ban, Nabolsi, Thultheen, Nassar, 2020). However, the global apprehension and anxiety due to COVID-19 might have worsened the psychological status of students. Depression, anxiety and stress might be observed apparently among students who lack the essential facilities of information technology that is needed to accomplish their online academic requirements. Lingelbach, Piechnik, Gado, Janssen, Eichler, Hentschel, Knopf, Schuler, Sernatinger and Peissner (2021) on their studies on effects of the COVID-19 Pandemic on psychological well-being and mental health. The result of the findings shows that the correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relation between age and wellbeing with younger participants revealing higher depression scores in the concerned cluster. Furthermore, multiple regression models revealed that the number of risk factors only has a significant influence on psychological well-being in the concerned but not in the comfortable cluster. Lorenzoni, Azzolina and Maresio (2022) study the impact of the COVID-19 lockdown on psychological health and nutritional habits in Italy: The results of their study reveals that out of respondents totalled 5008. Moderate or severe psychological distress was reported in 25.5% and 22% of survey respondents, respectively. Lower age, female gender, being unemployed (OR 1.57, 95% CI 1.22 to 2.02) or being a student (OR 1.73, 95% CI 1.31 to 2.28) were predictors of more severe depressive symptoms. Stachteas, Panagiotis & Stachteas (2020) examine the psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on secondary school teachers. The results of the test used to examine associations between psychological and other variables. 34% of teachers were found to feel anxious and very anxious during the pandemic, while only 8% of teachers exhibit severe depressive emotions. It is also clear that the educators as a professional group are predominantly possessed by optimism about the outcome of the pandemic, as 71.5% was placed in the higher levels of the relevant scale. Female gender was found to have a positive correlation to feelings of fear, depression, and a negative correlation to optimism. Furthermore, a negative correlation between the teachers' high educational level and their feelings of optimism emerged from the data. This optimism may well be related with the large acceptance of the measures taken by the government to curb the expansion of the pandemic. Finally, it was found that distance teaching, which was abruptly and unpreparedly implemented by educators on account of the pandemic, was not a major concern. The findings of our study indicate a specific profile of secondary school teachers characterized by mental

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resilience, a quality that must be exploited and strengthened by the state with appropriate interventions in order to maximize their complex, creative work.

Conclusion

1. Psychological anxiety due to event of covid-19 slightly impacts the students' self-efficacy in school of undergraduate studies Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare.
2. Psychological trauma of stress results from covid-19 pandemic moderately impacts self-efficacy among students of school of undergraduate studies Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare.
3. Students' self-efficacy has not been influenced by psychological trauma of depression in school of undergraduate studies Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare.
4. Students in School of Undergraduate Studies, Aminu Saleh College of Education, Azare were psychologically stressed due to Covid-19 pandemic.

5. Recommendations

1. Schools and educational stakeholders should play a fundamental role in assisting students to cope traumatic events that will result to psychological trauma. New guidelines for counseling are mandatory to be enacted and schools set priorities in developing digital psychological interventions, such as apps and online programs, alongside other services such as text messages, chatlines, forums, and phone calls.
2. There is need for stakeholders in the education ministries to recognize the need for an immediate and holistic policy to identify and manage the psychological impact of Covid-19 or any future pandemics on students and training and mindfulness therapy, which have been validated to reduce, anxiety, stress and depression levels.
3. There should be needs proper awareness on the presence of such traumatic events and to be clearly communicated to the student population in due time with provision of psychological services, either face to face or remotely, as they will mitigate the emotional and mental impacts on students
4. Government and non-governmental organizations should intensify community mindfulness, specifically for the students, by using artificial intelligence to obtain evidenced-based and scientific measures for pandemics and pandemic preparedness. Most importantly, an all-inclusive teaching and learning strategy during pandemics should be deliberated immediately, as this study confirms that the emergency remote teaching has contributed to significant psychological trauma and loss of self-efficacy among students.

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